

Empowerment Community in Buru Regency

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to identify the Empowerment Community which was held in the Buru Regency since the year 2005 to 2014. The approach used in this research using methods qualitative with the approach of the description, determination of informants using purposive with consideration of the informants are considered as related parties to achieve the research objectives. This study uses data collection techniques of observation, in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. Data analysis technique used to follow the concept of Miles, Huberman and Spradley. The results of the analysis of the data shows during the period 2005-2014 the implementation of empowerment in Buru Regency has not yet reached the value of the substance is visible of the low level of community understanding of the program overlapping the implementation of the program and the regional center as well as the dependence of the program on the system of budgeting. The results of the formulation of the empowerment model indicates there needs to be changes in the pattern of implementation of the empowerment program, namely the integration of Empowerment Community programs at the level of structure and operational. Hall program become central to the implementation of the program in a top-down and vice versa as well as have channels to avoid the buildup of empowerment programs in the area. Thus, the expected empowerment program more flexible to achieve the values of substantial and able to provide a solution to the problem of poverty

1. Introduction

In the context of regional development, Empowerment Community is one of the priorities of the Buru District Government policy in efforts to overcome poverty towards achieving the development vision of Buru Regency that is "Buru Regency Society Forward Towards A Healthy Bupolo, Smart, moral, prosperous and independent" (Chairul Basrun Umanailo). As known, alleviation of the poor is one of the priorities for medium and long term development in Buru Regency. This Empowerment Community policy is implemented through a variety of programs or activities both funded by the Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget and from various other sources, including the State Revenue and Expenditure Budget Buru Regency is one of the regions in Maluku Province with a relatively high poverty rate in the last 5 years (Afandi and Umanailo). this poverty problem, has directly affected the level of community welfare in Buru Regency, especially those in the countryside. Weak Empowerment Community in realizing prosperity is one indicator of the problem poverty (Solano Lara et al.). Various empowerment programs carried out by central and regional governments, it is known that it has not been able to answer various problems of poverty. Through research that has been done, known from 2005-2014 a number of Empowerment Community programs have been carried out in Buru Regency, but there are several problems that directly affect the sustainability of the program such as the target group, sustainability and the impact of the empowerment program. Dwi Pratiwi Kurniawati in a study of Empowerment Community in the field of economic business find a program that has been implemented by the Empowerment Community Agency of the City of Mojokerto especially in the Economic Business Sector covering individual assistance and institutional assistance has not been fully successful, dominance in the implementation by the local government made the program not run optimally (Kurniawati et al.). Meanwhile, Faizatul Karimah in his study of the management of village fund allocation in Empowerment Community showing normatively and administratively the management of village fund allocations is done well, but in substance it still has not touched the true meaning of empowerment (Karimah et al.). Achievement of indicators of Empowerment Community in the poor empowerment program Hairi Firmansyah's research shows that the indicators of Empowerment Community have not yet been achieved (level and basis of empowerment) (Prasetyono et al.) Isnan Murdiansyah shows several operational problems Gerdu-Taskin Program in Malang Regency like limited capital,

funding cuts, bad credit, domination of village officials, the support of village institutions and village governments is still low, and coordination between program managers in the district has not been maximized (Murdiansyah). The problems above, indicates the need for serious attention and fundamental improvement efforts in realizing public welfare through patterns of empowerment as an alternative to solving poverty. However, it became an evaluation for the government that the Empowerment Community activities that have been carried out so far are not a process of modernization and spurred an increase in production figures (Safitri). But the important thing is how to develop a climate conducive to the process of developing productive activities of the community based on their potential (Adamson).

Limited community conditions causing their ability to access economic resources to be very narrow (Rappaport). This situation has an impact on the low quality of life and welfare of the people in Buru Regency. Thus the need for treatment to protect life (Bektas and Sohrabifard) provide counseling, guidance and assistance in the process of Empowerment Community, especially concerning the issue of food security. This study was designed to be able to identify socio-economic problems in the Buru Regency and formulate a food resilience Empowerment Community model. Therefore, what is expected from the output produced is an empowerment model for increasing community independence.

The study was directed to see in general the implementation of Empowerment Community programs in Buru Regency. other than that, descriptively the study was directed to explain the implementation of pre-existing Empowerment Community programs (Loh and Agyeman), by using general indicators, namely planning, objectives, process or program approach, suitability of the program with needs, continuity of the program, the role of facilitators and community participation. Thus it will be a practical approach in the form of an integrated Empowerment Community model. The model is an input to policy makers to form an empowerment program model that is appropriate based on the socio-economic conditions of the people in the rural areas of Buru regency.

2. Research methods

The research was carried out in 8 villages in the Regency Buru, Maluku Province. Site selection is done at random with the consideration that the village has been selected to represent the characteristics of the community among other things; Highlands Community, the lowlands and coastal communities. The time used in this research is for 60 (sixty) calendar days beginning in February through August 2018. As for the research conducted by the method of qualitative and descriptive analysis approach.

The main data sources in qualitative research is the words and actions, the rest is additional data such as photo documentation, recording and other similar writings. With regard to data, its type can be divided into words and action, the data source is written, photo and stats (Maxwell and Reibold). In this study the author's data gathering techniques use is deep interview with the community on the eight villages of samples as well as observations directly to the object of research (Somantri). By utilizing the custom community who love to congregate at night, then the interview is done starting at 19:00-23:00.

For data analysis, the author uses at the time of data collection underway, and after the completion of data collection within a certain period. By analyzing data while collecting, the writer can know firsthand the lack of data should be collected as well as methods to do next in order to obtained the results of a comprehensive.

By doing the presentation of data, researchers can work more quickly and precisely in coding and decision making based on the focus of the research. The presentation of the data is an integral part of data analysis qualitative research (Umanailo). Presentation of data analysis as part of the reduction was also part of data analysis The presentation of data in qualitative research in General IE matrix, graphs, charts, and text narrative. Withdrawal/verification conclusion is the end of the analysis of qualitative research data. The withdrawal was done with such conclusions through reflection data (Marshall).

3. Result And Discussion

Alleviation of the poor is one of the priorities of the medium-term development and long term in a hurry. Empowerment Community policy is implemented through a variety of programs or activities of the well sourced the funds from the budget of income and expenditure area (APBD) as well as from various other sources, including the budget of income and expenditure State (APBN).

Through a structured development planning can identify problems of development facing so that it could formulate programs empowerment based on the analysis of the socio-economic potential which is owned by the community.

Tabel 1.Type of Main Employment Field Population in Buru Regency in 2016

Main Employment Field	Gender		
	Man	Women	Total
Agriculture, Forestry, Hunting and Fisheries	14.102	6.421	20.523
Mining and excavation	1.758	167	1.925
Processing industry	4.001	1.533	5.534
Electricity of Gas and Water	0	0	0
Bagunan	3.245	40	3.285
Trade, Retail, Restaurants and Hotels	3.743	5.439	9.182
Transportation, Warehousing and Communication	3.785	0	3.785
Finance, Insurance, Building Rental Business, Land and Company Services	508	55	623
Community, Social and Individual Services	4.276	3.819	7.438
Total	35.476	17.474	52.952

Source: *Buru District People's Welfare Indicator 2017*

Community conditions that limited their ability to cause in accessing economic resources being very minimal. Poverty is one of the indicators of vulnerability of communities in accessing economic resources (Perkins and Zimmerman), but amid the socioeconomic conditions are still faced with the problem of poverty that directly impact on the poor quality of life and the welfare of society in Buru regency. Regarding poverty (Bradley) in Buru Regency, based on data obtained, the number of poor people in Buru Regency in the last three years has increased. In 2016 it increased compared to 2015. In 2015, the number of poor people was 23,440 people and then increased in 2016 to 23,530 people (BPS, 2017).

As a wrong strategy in regional development, Empowerment Community policies through economic development and empowerment programs and community food security in Buru Regency are expected to protect them from the risk of poverty.

Table 2. Implementation of the Empowerment Program

No	Type of Assistance	Year	Source	Form of Assistance
1	PNPM Mandiri	2007	central government	Mandiri Direct Assistance, Mentoring, Training
2	PKPS BBM	2005	central government	Education, health, rural infrastructure
4	Program Keluarga Harapan (PKH)	2007	central government	Money for education and health
5	GerduTaskin	2005	provincial government	Venture capital
6	PEMP	2003	central government	Economic improvement, Human Resources, social economic strengthening of coastal communities
7	KUBE	-	central government	Community productive business development
8	SOLID	2014	central government	Increased productivity of integrated farming systems, institutional strengthening and Empowerment Community and gender
9	P2KP	2002	central government	Poverty alleviation
10	Dana Desa	2014	central government	Infrastructure, Human Resource Development and Empowerment Community
11	PNPM Mandiri KP	2010	central government	Cash Direct Assistance
12	PUMP-PB	2012	central government	Direct Cash Assistance for Fisheries Cultivation Development

Source: Primary Data processed in 2018

The empowerment programs above, based on the results of field studies show that participation factors become dominant and important factors. Participation in the sense of the Group's involvement of the poor in a whole series of processes of empowerment, from the identification of problems and needs to the utilization of the results of empowerment. It can be seen from the community involvement in the preparation of the program and the level of empowerment of the community against the introduction of a source of empowerment Fund.

Based on previous reviews, Note that to date the effectiveness of poverty alleviation programmes which have been tested by the Government which is either top-down or bottom-up votes still have not been able to walk properly (Bublitz et al.). It is characterized by low levels of success of programs are top-down target program because the public is not involved in the determination of the programs and activities of monitoring and evaluation so that people like getting grants from the government and do not have to restore again (Spreitzer). Programs that are bottom up so well despite its failure rate is lower compared with the top down.

For a successful Empowerment Community program, institutional aspects (Solano Lara et al.) for Empowerment Community program is a very important support resources. It takes a strong institutional (Mao et al.), rooted (Fernandez and Moldogaziev) representative (Fuchs and Schreier) for Empowerment Community programs that are able to synergize the entire stakeholder Empowerment Community program (Government & non governmental) able to afford to be a motivator in the community towards a better change. Next in order for Empowerment Community efforts well underway, the presence of the "Hall program" is indispensable.

The primary responsibility in the program is the community development helpless or has power, strength or ability (Perkins and Zimmerman). The power in question can be seen from the physical and material aspects, economic, institutional, intellectual power and cooperation, shared commitment in applying the principles of empowerment (Bulte and Lensink). In the picture below, shows the scheme that was built was the alignment between the strength of the institutional and human resources. In general the grand design illustrates the existence of distribution of the program in the "hall program" where the overall focus of activities is on the control of the "hall program".

Figure 1. Elaboration Of Institutional Empowerment Community Model

Sources of empowerment that comes from private parties, the Central Government as well as provincial government (Adamson) through the Canal heading to the "hall program" and so also with the empowerment resources originating from Buru Regency Government will tag along on the Canal towards "hall program". It is intended to create an integrated and accelerated management program – the program empowerment are integral (Luo et al.), So what was planned and who want to generated does not happen partially.

Elaboration of institutional is a description of the subject matter regarding the circulation and distribution channel grouping and proposing of empowerment programs sourced from the Central Government and the regions as well as from private parties (Kaasinen et al.).

Empowerment of private parties in the form of aid or grants program, in its implementation should participate on the channel so that in planning and implementing more focused on institutional undergoing the program. So are a variety of programs that come from the Central Government in this Ministry or ministerial institution, the provincial government, need to be included on channel program that leads to the "hall program" in the implementation of the necessary empowerment of intrinsic values in societies that also became a source of strength, like family values, co-operation and unity. Independence of the community are elements that allow a society survive, and in the sense of a dynamic develop themselves and achieve progress. self-reliance community became a source of what it called political insight in national resilience.

4. Conclusion

Empowerment Community is a process that aims to change. Empowerment Community is an effort to provide opportunities to the community at the same time the ability to play an active role in the development. One of the positive impact of Empowerment Community program implementation, is the community is able to take responsibility towards their work. of research results and the above discussion can be taken a few conclusions.

Buru Regency is one of the areas in Maluku Province with potential natural resources abundant enough accompanied by the strength of local cultural life of community support for the achievement of well-being. From the beginning up to the present already formed a considerable amount of Empowerment Community programmes provide deit her by the central government and the regions as poverty reduction and the improvement of well-being. Empowerment programs based individuals and groups as community development efforts tend to overlap in one region of the implementation, lack of concentration and focus on the process and impact of programs implemented so that happened during this is empowerment in partial form and lack of synchronization and verification of the database or the individual target group.

Weak data synchronization and networking oportunites for work program occurred attenuation of programs that have an impact on the target product so the program empowerment more stop on the implementation process and target group.

The empowerment model integrates the findings of the implementation model is divided into two parts, institutional and operational basis to ease the process of implementation of the activities and the preparation of various instruments. The empowerment model integrates ease of initiation society to convey the proposals as well as stimulate the creativity of individuals and target groups in the implementation of Empowerment Community.

Hall became the center of program implementation of the program that integrates the initiation, the process of implementation to monitoring and reporting the end of Empowerment Community team empowerment of village community became an important pillar for the process of implementation and accompaniment towards individuals or target groups in each village. The main source of initiation is derived from a structured society up to the hall program which are divided into internal initiation and sharing programs against the central government, local government or private parties.

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Biographies

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Rosita Umanailo is one of the agricultural lecturers of the University of Iqra Buru who chose to concentrate on the social field of agriculture. Completed undergraduate studies on University of Muhammadiyah Malang with research results on changes in farmer behaviour. Currently it is still running research activities about land function and diversification of agriculture focused on rural areas.

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Riki Bugis is a lecturer who serves in the Faculty of Literature Iqra University Buru. Completed study of Humanities at Hasanuddin University with English language education study. Riki is part of a university research team that participates in community empowerment through cultural education developed by the Center for Planning and Community Development studies. One of the results of research studies published is the role of local language in community empowerment.

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